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Languages in contemporaneity

The academic journal "**Revista Letras Raras**," focused on Linguistics and Literature, from the Laboratory of Studies in Letters and Languages in Contemporaneity at the Federal University of Campina Grande, is releasing its third regular edition for the year 2023. This edition features a dossier organized by professors Alain-Philippe Durand from the University of Arizona, Josilene Pinheiro-Mariz from the Federal University of Campina Grande, and Maria Rennally Soares da Silva from the Federal University of Paraíba.

The thirteen articles that compose the dossier titled "Languages in Contemporaneity" cover areas such as Language Dialogism, Sociodiscursive Interactionism, Discourse Analysis, Beliefs, Applied Linguistics, Didactics, Media Genres, Indigenous Literature, Comparative Literature, Literary Adaptation for Cinema, and Literary Reception. The edition also includes a literary translation of a text originally published in English, along with four texts of artistic creation.

This edition has the collaboration of teachers, students at different levels of study and researchers who are authors of the articles, translations, and artistic or literary texts. They come from diverse institutions such as the University of Coimbra, Federal University of Northern Tocantins - UFNT, Federal University of Paraíba - UFPB, Federal University of Rio Grande - FURG, Federal Fluminense Institute of Education, Science, and Technology - IFFluminense, Federal University of Mato Grosso do Sul - UFMTS, Federal Center for Technological Education of Minas Gerais - CEFET-MG, Federal University of Campina Grande - UFCG, State University of Paraíba (UEPB), State University of Rio Grande do Norte - UERN, Federal University of Rio Grande do Norte - UFRN, Pontifical Catholic University of Minas Gerais - PUC Minas, Federal Rural University of Rio de Janeiro - UFRRJ, State University of Mato Grosso - UNEMAT, State University of Ceará - UECE, Municipal Network of Campos dos Goytacazes - SMECE/PMCG, and Duque de Caxias - SMEDC/PMDC.

Dear reader, in this third regular edition, you can share texts from this dossier by pointing your smartphone camera at the journal's QR code for the desired text. Share the article, translation, or poem from this issue with your colleagues and students.

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With certainty in this sharing, dear reader, we wish you happy holidays and excellent reading!

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Translated by Rafael de Arruda Sobral